

Effect of Rheological Properties on the Coagulation of Emulsion Droplets under Isoelectric Conditions

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The role of visco-elastic characteristics of the protein film in the coagulation of petroleum-water emulsions, established by bovine serum albumin, has been investigated. On addition of certain surfactants to the protein-covered hydrocarbon droplets at the isoelectric point, the rate of coagulation increases. This variation, which is a function of the rheology of the protein film, has been studied quantitatively.

The BSA (bovine serum albumin) films are known to be visco-elastic at hydrocarbon/water interfaces. The role of such films in emulsion formation and subsequent stabilisation has been recognised by many workers. Reh binder and Tranpeznikov¹ found that their O/W emulsions were remarkably stable due to visco-elastic properties of the interfacial protein film. The same conclusion was reached by Cumper and Alexander², who attributed the stabilisation of O/W emulsions to the mechanical protection by the protein film. Recently Biswas and Haydon^{3,4} have shown a close parallelism between stability and the mechanical properties of the protein film.

In the present work, the significance of the viscosity or elasticity of the protein film in the stability of the emulsion droplets has been shown by studying the flocculation and coalescence in presence of surface active agents, such as phenol, decanol, and an equimolar mixture of sodium tetradecyl sulphate and tetradecyltrimethylammonium bromide. On the addition of these ionic and non-ionic detergents to the emulsions, the protein coatings round the oil globules are displaced and the viscosity and elasticity fall⁴. Under these conditions the rates of both coalescence and flocculation usually increase. This variation is a function of the rheology of the protein films and has been studied under constant electrical conditions at the isoelectric point of BSA-coated droplets.

The breaking of an emulsion comprises flocculation and coalescence. Kinetically flocculation is bimolecular and is represented by the equation:

$$-dn_1/dt = K_1 n_0^2$$

or
$$1/n_1 - 1/n_0 = K_1 t \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where n_0 is the number of oil droplets present initially and n_1 is the number of primary particles taking part in the flocculation process; K_1 , the Smoluchowski's rate constant, denotes the frequency of collisions between oil droplets and is governed by the repulsive forces between them.

1. *Acta Physico-chim., URSS*, 1936, 62, 257.
2. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1950, 46, 252.
3. III Int. Cong. Surface Activity, 1960, 2B, p. 584.
4. *Koll. Z. Polymere*, 1962, 185, 32.

Coalescence, on the other hand, is unimolecular and is represented by the equation:

$$-dn_2/dt = Kn_2$$

$$\text{or} \quad \ln n_0 - \ln n_2 = K_2 t \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$$\text{or} \quad n_2 = n_0 e^{-K_2 t}$$

where n_2 is the number of individual emulsion drops and K_2 is the rate of coalescence; it depends on the lateral adhesion properties of the stabiliser film in the interface. If, therefore, the overall rate follows a unimolecular equation, coalescence will evidently be the rate-determining process. From equations (1) and (2), $t_{1/2} = 1/K_1 n_0$, where $t_{1/2}$ is half-time of flocculation; $t'_{1/2} = 1/K_2$, where $t'_{1/2}$ is half-time of coalescence. Therefore, half-life could be determined as a function of n_0 by suitably diluting the emulsion. Alternatively, one could calculate the ratio, $K_1 n_0 / K_2$, which will be $\gg$ or $\ll$ unity according as flocculation or coalescence occurs more rapidly.

EXPERIMENTAL

Crystallised BSA of Armour Pharmaceutical Company and AnalaR petroleum* (b.p. 120-180°, density 0.75 g./ml at 20°) were used. Other materials were of AnalaR grade. Pyrex glassware and double distilled water were used.

FIG. 1. Plot of $1/n_2$ against time for diff. conc. of phenol.

Emulsions were prepared by suspending 1.0% purified petroleum in aqueous 0.01 M KCl solution containing 0.01% BSA and subsequently homogenising the mixture with a centrifugal MSE homogeniser. The freshly formed emulsion (O/W) was allowed to stand for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. and then the creamed layer skimmed off. The sampling was done under identical conditions.

Determination of the rate of coagulation was carried out by counting the number of oil droplets haemocytometrically. Under normal conditions, the initial particle concentration was 7.4×10^7 globules/ml and pH of the emulsion was 5.4. The emulsion was rendered isoelectric (pH 5.0) with a Cambridge pH-meter. All the experiments were carried out at 20°. Rheological data were taken from the work of Biawas and Haydon⁴.

*The petroleum used always refers to the boiling range 120-80°.

Rate of Flocculation.—To study the influence of the surface active agents on the rate of flocculation of the BSA emulsions, the reciprocal of the number of primary particles present at any instant ($1/n_t$) was plotted against time. Only the representative curves for phenol are shown in Fig. 1 and for the detergents, decanol and a mixture of $n\text{-C}_{14}\text{H}_{29}\text{SO}_4\text{Na}$ and $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{29}(\text{CH}_3)\text{NBr}$ (henceforth referred to as $\text{C}_{14}\text{SO}_4^- + \text{Q}$), necessary numerical data have been reported. For the sake of comparison all the curves are under constant electrical conditions, i.e., at the isoelectric point of the emulsion. Constant concentrations of 0.01% BSA and of 0.01M-KCl were maintained throughout except otherwise stated. It may be observed from the graphs that the rate of flocculation increases with the increasing concentration of the surfactant (surface active agent). This is further illustrated in Table I where the different values of Smoluchowski's rate constant, K_1 , have been calculated on the basis of equation (1).

TABLE I

Effect of detergents on the flocculation of BSA emulsions at the isoelectric point.

Detergent conc. (m/litre)	$K_1 \times 10^{12}$ ($\text{cm}^3 \text{sec}^{-1}$)	$K_2 \times 10^6$ (sec^{-1})	Detergent conc. (m/litre)	$K_1 \times 10^{12}$ ($\text{cm}^3 \text{sec}^{-1}$)	$K_2 \times 10^6$ (sec^{-1})	Detergent conc. (m/litre)	$K_1 \times 10^{12}$ ($\text{cm}^3 \text{sec}^{-1}$)	$K_2 \times 10^6$ (sec^{-1})
1. Without detergent.			3. Decanol.			4. $\text{C}_{14}\text{SO}_4^- + \text{Q}$.		
0.000	1.66	5.50						
2. Phenol								
0.005	2.47	9.55	0.2×10^{-3}	3.46	10.70	1.5×10^{-6}	2.09	9.30
0.010	3.14	11.60				2.0	2.31	..
0.020	4.09	15.40	0.8	6.25	15.40	2.5	3.30	15.40
0.040	6.40	19.80	1.6	7.90	18.50	4.0	4.00	18.50
0.060	11.00	..	4.0	10.50	21.30	1.0	8.65	19.80

FIG. 2. Coalescence of the emulsion in presence of phenol.

Rate of Coalescence

The rate of coalescence of emulsions, as determined from $\ln n_t$ vs. t graphs (equation 2) is also found to increase on addition of the surfactants. This is denoted by the representative graphs in Fig. 2 for phenol at the isoelectric point. It is seen that rates of coalescence, K_2 , as shown in Table I (also Fig. 3), decrease with the amount of the additive due to removal of the protein film (hence its rigidity) covering over the emulsion globules. As is seen from the graphs (Fig. 4) of variation of n_0 with time, the process of coalescence is found to be rate-determining. Again, when BSA is removed, the emulsion drops may be appreciably negative. It was thought of interest to try the same system with higher electrolytic concentrations. On carrying out the dilution test at 0.04M-KCl, coalescence was found to be still the rate-determining process.

This suggests that the negative charge is not important and that the protein is displaced only partially.

FIG. 3. Rate of coalescence as a function of log molar conc. of the added detergent.

Influence of BSA Concentration

To ascertain the dependence of the BSA film thickness on the conditions of the formation of the interface, flocculation and coalescence were also studied, using different concentrations of BSA (0.005%, 0.1%, 0.2%) in addition to the concentration of 0.01% used normally. For this the experiments were carried out in two ways. In one set, the emulsion was actually prepared in the final concentration of BSA. In the second set, the emulsion was prepared in 0.001% BSA and aged for 30 minutes and then the concentration of BSA made up to the desired final value. No appreciable difference in either the rate of flocculation or the rate of coalescence could be detected. This is in conformity with the fact that the adsorption of BSA is not a function of its bulk concentration⁵; so the thickness of the film will remain unaffected. As observed by Biswas and Haydon⁴, the rheology of the film is also independent of the protein concentration.

DISCUSSION

Role of Surface Elasticity

The value of Smoluchowski's constant, K_1 (1.66×10^{-12}), as obtained in absence of any detergent, is about 10 times lower than the theoretical value. In Table I,

5. Cookbain, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1956, 11, 575.

however, it can be seen that the value of K_1 increases with the increase of the concentration of the surfactant added at the isoelectric point of the emulsion. This is due to the destructive influence of the small molecules of the detergents on the rheological properties of the film of the stabilising macromolecule. Quantitatively it may be interpreted as follows.

FIG. 4. Variation of n_0 in presence of phenol(0.04M).

In view of the Maxwellian distribution of Brownian velocities, the retarded rate constant, K_1 , for slow flocculation, when all the collisions are not effective due to the presence of an energy barrier of value E , is given by the equation:

$$K_1 = K_0 e^{-E/kT} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant and T , the absolute temperature.

Now, if the partial effectivity of the collisions is attributable to the film elasticity, one may guess that

$$E = f(G_s)$$

where G_s , the shear modulus of surface elasticity = $\frac{G_0 - G}{G_0}$, G_0 and G being the elasticities

of the pure protein film and in the presence of the detergent respectively, and assuming a linear function.

$$E = \text{constant} \times G_s$$

Equation (3) is thus found to yield

$$\log K = \log K_0 - \frac{\text{constant}}{2.303kT} G_s \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Since the value of G_s is also conditioned by the pH of the emulsion, the plot of $\log K$ against G_s for the increasing concentrations of the detergent at the neutral point of the charge should be a straight line. The linear plots, thus obtained (Fig. 5), when extrapolated to zero elasticity, i.e. absence of a stabilising protein film, provided the value of $K_1 = 1.62 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ in case of phenol, $= 1.78 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ in case of decanol, and $= 1.58 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ in case of $C_{14}SO_4$ and quaternary salt mixture. These correspond to an average value for the rapid rate constant of $1.5 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$. This is approximately the value expected theoretically, considering polydispersity of the system.

FIG. 5 $\log K_1$ vs. G_s in presence of phenol (from extrapolation ($K_0 = 1.622 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$)).

To gain further insight into the above hypothesis, one has to consider the nature of the constant in equation (4). The values of the constant, C_1 , as calculated from the tangents of the plots of $\log K_1$ versus G_2 and energies of desorption are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Detergent.	C_1 (ergs/molecule)	Energies of desorption (kcal./mole).
Phenol	9.2×10^{-14}	1.33
Decanol	7.7×10^{-14}	1.11
$C_{14}SO_4^- + Q$	14.7×10^{-14}	2.16

The values of the constant C_1 are of the same order of magnitude as the value of the van der Waals constant⁶ of BSA (2×10^{-14} erg) and correspond to the energies of desorption of the protein film. Since to desorb the film, work has to be done against the attraction between the protein molecules, the order of magnitude of the desorption energies appears to be correct. Thus the hypothesis propounded appears to be justified.

Role of Surface Viscosity

In their work on the coalescence of droplets, stabilised by visco-elastic films against a plane interface, Biswas and Hayden³⁻⁴ have concluded that an appreciable stabilisation is attainable only when, apart from its viscoelasticity, the film is of sufficient thickness and lies towards the continuous phase. The same conclusion seems to apply to the coalescence of the emulsion droplets as in the present work, where, of course, electrostatic characteristics of the system are of primary importance. Although it is difficult to sort out the relative importance of the two rheological parameters in emulsion stability, it seems more probable that viscosity retards coalescence, just as elasticity inhibits rapid flocculation. Therefore, regardless of the relative contribution of the intrinsic rheology of the film, a definite conclusion is that the visco-elastic nature of the adsorbed film of the macromolecule does play a distinct part in the overall rate, namely, of the coagulation of the emulsion. The correlation, however, is not entirely straight-forward in a quantitative sense.

Relative Rates of Flocculation and Coalescence

On calculating the values of the ratio, $K_1 n_0 / K_2$, the ranges obtained are 19.2 to 23.9—36.4 and 16.1 to 34 for increasing concentrations of phenol, decanol, and $C_{14}SO_4^- + Q$ mixture respectively. This denotes that coalescence is still slower and hence the rate determining process. There is also the tendency of the ratio to increase with the increasing concentration of the surfactant, indicating thereby that as the film becomes thinner or loses its rigidity, the rate of flocculation increases more rapidly than coalescence.

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